

FUNCTION OF ADJECTIVES "NOTES OF HUNTER"

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As you already know, the adjective is- the part of speech, which denotes the attribute of an object. In our article we want to reveal the functions of adjectives and categories in the works of I.S. Turgenev "Notes of a Hunter".

Analyzing the works of Turgenev, we observe how the writer praising beauty, telling the life of a hunter, using words and expressions in the most beautiful forms, and the most optimal linguistic device he used for this purpose was the adjective.

We believe it is important to focus on features, which serve as adjectives - components of synonymous series in fiction. So, for a literary text, the characterological function of linguistic means is one of the most important, since the writer strives to give an accurate, detailed emotional description of the characters, and also the events, objects, and natural phenomena described in the work. For a writer, it is very important to create a portrait of characters and describe their appearance.

For example, "The Oryol peasant is short, stooped, gloomy, looks from under his brows, lives in crappy aspen huts. "Corvee man from the story "Khor and Kalinich" by I.S. Turgenev. In this context, adjectives have semantics: Orlovsky is a person living in the Oryol region, not large - this is a short adjective meaning small.

Stooped - hunched over, crappy - bad, aspen - this is a relative adjective meaning a house made of aspen.

The characterizing function can also be performed in dialogue: “But here’s why: he’s a smart guy - an all-knowing guy. The syntactic role of an adjective depends on its form - short or full. To determine the syntactic role of any part of speech, you need to ask the right question. For instance, the Orlovsky man is short, stooped, gloomy: “Orlovsky” (which one?) in the sentence is in full form and is a definition, and the adjective “small, gloomy, stooped” (what?) In a sentence they are in short form and are predicates. We use adjectives for emotional and expressive coloring in works of art and speech. There are three types of adjectives: qualitative, relative and possessive.

Qualitative adjectives denote the qualities of objects directly without relation to other objects. For example, in the story "Two Landowners" he used about 185 adjectives. With these adjectives, he was able to beautifully describe the appearance of the characters and nature. He utilized qualitative adjectives more.

To put an example, “Mardarius Apollonich is an old man, short, plump, bald, with a double chin, soft arms and a decent belly.” With the help of these qualitative adjectives he described his appearance and also in this story he used such qualitative adjectives as “tall, slender, not decrepit, poor, unofficial” and the like. Relative adjectives name a characteristic through its relationship to other objects, materials, time, space, actions. For example, “On a nice summer day, he orders the running tracks to be laid out and goes to the field to look at the grain and pick cornflowers.”

In this context, I.S. Turgenev used the relative adjectives “summer and running,” denoting characteristics through the relationship of time and action. The famous linguist Yu.S. Stepanov believed that the difference between the qualitative and relative meanings of adjectives is one of the most difficult, and possessive adjectives denote belonging. I.S. Turgenev rarely used possessive adjectives.

The story "The Office" from the series "Notes of a Hunter" I.S. Turgenev begins with a description of nature and the road: “It was in the fall. I had already been

wandering through the fields with a gun for several hours and, probably, before the evening I would not have returned to the inn on the large Kurskaya village, where my troika was waiting for me, if the extremely fine and cold rain, which from the very morning, no worse than an old girl, pestered me restlessly and mercilessly, had not finally forced me.

In this context, adjectives have semantics: inn (yard) - an inn with places to stay overnight and a yard for horses and carts", large - of significant size, small - consisting of small homogeneous particles, cold - having a low temperature, not heated, not giving or not containing heat, the earliest - the earliest or the most used to clarify.

Conclusion: The role of adjectives in any work is significant. It is through adjectives writers can convey to the reader all the beauty of what they describe realities.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. E.S. Simakova. Russian language: New complete reference book for preparing for the Unified State Exam / 2nd edition, revised and expanded - Moscow: AST Publishing House, 2016. [p.187]
2. N.Yu.Shvedova. Russian Grammar / Syntax [vol.2]. M.: Nauka, 1980.
3. The series "Notes of a Hunter". 1847-1874. M., "Forest industry", 1980. [p. 3 – 15, 154 – 162, 129 – 145]